

CHADA

Characterisation Data and description of a characterisation experiment

For [*Impedance Spectroscopy for Organic Photovoltaic Samples*]

Used in [MMAMA]

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Overview of EIS Characterisation

1 Sample	Materials for Organic photovoltaic (OPV) devices. The samples consist of an organic semiconductor or a photovoltaic blend of two materials to be analysed and located between two electrodes along with an insulating layer to form a Metal (gate)-Insulator-Semiconductor-Metal (counter electrode) test structure.
2 Method	Impedance spectroscopy (IS) method utilized consists of applying an alternating voltage signal ($V(t) = V_0 \exp(i\omega t)$, with $\omega = 2\pi f$, where ω is the angular frequency, and f is the signal frequency) between the electrodes of the device under test (DUT) which induces an alternating current AC ($I(t) = I_0 \exp(i\omega t - i\varphi)$, where φ is the phase between the induced current $I(t)$ and the applied voltage $V(t)$). DC bias is superimposed to the modulation to vary the semiconducting regime of the DUT (depletion or accumulation) The impedance of the DUT is calculated as $Z = V(t)/I(t)$ and the corresponding admittance is $Y = I(t)/V(t)$. Both impedance and admittance are complex values.). As the DUT exhibits MIS structures, admittance measurements are preferred to impedance ones. The conductance is the real part ($\text{real}\{Y\} = G$) of the admittance and the susceptance is the imaginary part ($\text{imag}\{Z\} = B$). Key parameters are the loss ($L(\omega)$) and capacitance ($C(\omega)$), corresponding to the conductance and susceptance divided by the angular frequency (ω). The frequency dependence of the DUT is used to separate the different electrical contributions from the total response. IS measurements can be technically carried out across a 7-10 orders of magnitude of frequency (1 mHz and 120 MHz), although for a best trade-off efficiency/measurement time, operating from 1 Hz upwards is sufficient.
3 Data publication	A joint scientific publication is targeted. An original data set is uploaded to the open innovation environment and Zenodo, with the MD5 checksum: 14c700819b9b94de532219536e4b5e89 Link to contribution: https://zenodo.org/record/4138701#.X76EKHdFxPY
4 Access conditions	Open innovation environment and Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) A direct link to be added after publication.

5 Workflow of the characterisation

Raw data acquisition of the Impedance Spectroscopy method for characterization of organic photovoltaic samples is done as follows:

Preliminary determination of additional contributions from device circuitry with series resistance to be reduced as much as possible to increase the sensitivity of the impedance measurement in highest frequency range. Corresponding calibration DUT for preliminary tests also include a gate oxide between the gate electrode and the device wiring, electrodes, and interfacial layer. This serves also to determine shunt resistance and validate DUT. Then the MIS like DUT with the semiconducting materials to be characterised is measured. The impedance analyser terminals with a voltage signal applied are connected via shielded cables to the positive and negative electrodes using (+, -) of the impedance analyser and the induced current between both electrodes is measured. The voltage $V(t)$ and current $I(t)$ across the terminals are digitized and transformed into the frequency domain, where the actual admittance $Y(\omega)=1/Z(\omega)$ then converted into Loss $L(\omega)$ and capacitance $C(\omega)$ are computed. Initial variations of C with DC bias at low frequency is recorded to span between depletion and accumulation of the semiconductor regime. In this process frequency sweeping is then used for the excitation signal to cover the whole spectrum e.g. from Hz to GHz. Several spectra are recorded at different DC bias. The resulting data is stored, analysed and corroborated by different complex impedance plots. External determination of the thickness of the semiconducting film is necessary for additional determination of carrier mobility with $\mu = \frac{q}{kT} t^2 f_0$ with t the film thickness, and f_0 the frequency corresponding to the maximum loss.

IS Workflow Picture

Figure 1. CHADA workflow for IS-OPV

1. Sample		
1.1	USER	Human operator. Typically, EIS characterization measurements are done by electrical engineers, electro-chemists, or practical physicist. The level of automation is partially ensured by customized Matlab codes for data extraction and compilation
1.2	User case (sample specifications)	<p>The typical MIS structure of the sample under test can be fabricated on glass substrate as shown in Figure 2 but also any other insulating substrates:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ITO (indium tin oxide) partially covered with aluminium (“Al bus”) is the bottom electrode (the gate), i.e. the “M” of the MIS structure. The Al bus is used to lower the internal series resistances of the device. • The alumina (Al_2O_3) is this Insulator (gate dielectric). • The Organic Semiconductor is the material to be investigated. • An interlayer is used to functionalize the electrode to ensure ohmic contact for carrier injection/collection from the top electrode (Al) into the Organic Semiconductor. The interlayer is defined according to the type of carriers, hence the semiconducting type to be probed: MoO_3 for hole (p-type) probing; Yb for electrons (n-type). This allows the monitoring of carrier probing across p-type/n-type photovoltaic blends. <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 2. MIS architecture as used in this work.</i></p>
1.3	Specimen	Organic semiconductor (SC) in a Metal-Insulator-SC-interfacial Layer-Metal device – Different possible substrates: glass, plastic. For air testing environment, device encapsulation is mandatory: 50 nm Al_2O_3 deposited by ALD (Atomic Layer Deposition).
1.4	Testing environment	Measurement is carried in ambient conditions provided the sample is encapsulated. If not, inert atmosphere is required to prevent quick degradation of the electrical properties of the material under study.
1.5	Material	The device architecture chosen is a so-called Metal-Insulator-Semiconductor (MIS) structure (or also referred in the scientific literature as Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (MOS) structure, when the insulator is an oxide (typically Al_2O_3).

2. Method		
2.1	Sample/probe physics of interaction	Sample is attached to the probe by a coaxial cable directly contacting the sample electrodes. A stimulus voltage signal is applied to the sample and the response to this stimulus is detected. The physics of interaction is based on Ohm's law $V(\omega) = I(\omega) / Z(\omega)$ or $I(\omega) = V(\omega) / Y(\omega)$ DC bias can be superimposed on the modulation.
2.2	Volume of interaction	Full volume of sample.
2.3	Equipment setup	The Impedance Analyzer is connected through coaxial wiring to the test fixture then to the sample under test.
2.4	Calibration	<p>Standards short, open and load are used for calibration. The load standard contains a precisely characterized resistor prepared in a fixture design like the sample under test. The fixture compensation is done by open and short calibration.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p><i>Figure 3. Calibration workflow for IS-OPV</i></p>
2.5	Probe	Arbitrary wave generator in the impedance analyser is used to drive the output amplifier which is used in constant voltage (CV) mode.
2.6	Detector	The current AC component is sensed by the impedance analyser and digitized coherently with the original voltage signal.
2.7	Signal	Sinusoidal voltage signal, $V_{pp}=100$ mV.
2.8	Time lapse	Depending on the resolution, number of points and frequency range the acquisition time can vary. Low frequency points require more time (e.g. at 10 mHz about 1.7min are needed to get the data at that point). Therefore [1 Hz; 120 MHz] appears the best trade off data/time ratio for measurements

2.9	Testing Input parameters	Frequency start and stop, frequency points, excitation voltage and drive level, integration time.
2.10	Main acquired channels	Current (amplitude and phase-shift) induced in sample. Voltage generated in impedance Analyser.

3. Raw data

3.1	Raw Data	Raw admittance as a function of frequency is computed, containing in its amplitude and phase key parameters like conductance and susceptance to be converted in meaningful information like loss and capacitance, and resistance. This determination of properties results from digitizing the current and voltage across the sample terminals and transforming them into the frequency domain where the actual admittance is measured.
3.2	Data acquisition rate	10k samples/sec – 100 samples/sec

4. Data processing

4.1	Main data filtering processes	Down-sampling + FIR filtering is done depending on the IS frequency and speed settings
4.2	Main data analysis procedures	Frequency sweep for input signal, pre-processing (filtering and windowing), applying Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) for both current and voltage signals, then analytic calculation of admittance $Y(\omega)=I(\omega)/V(\omega)$, followed signal processing with error correction based on the extracted calibration coefficients.
4.3	Main processed channels	One channel is used to source the voltage through the DUT terminals while sensing the current between the DUT terminals.
4.4	Data processing through calibrations	The systematic error correction is processed by defining an appropriate error model and measuring certain calibration standards in order to solve for the error coefficients.
4.5	Properties (elaborated data)	The complex calibrated admittance variations with frequency are separated into magnitude and phase data or real and imaginary values, the latter representing the conductance and susceptance and from which are defined the loss and the capacitance respectively. Capacitance variations with DC bias serves to monitor the semiconductor regime and the maximum loss frequency to determine the carrier mobility in the semiconductor.